

Design and Implementation of an Autonomous Control System based on microcontroller Arduino for use in Logistics

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Abstract

In this paper, we will explore some of the exciting use cases for IoT in logistics and cluster these within the bounds of warehousing operations and freight transportation. The Internet of Things (IoT) is a term coined to describe the communication between machine to machine through Internet connectivity. Utilizing this network infrastructure, logistic processes can also be managed much more efficiently and effectively. Transportation used to be the weakest link when it comes to logistics due to the limited security measures available to ensure the safe delivery of the cargo. By using the concept of IoT, and using sensors to communicate between the shipper and carrier, logistics service providers are able to see and manage their freight and drivers on a much larger scale, whether it's the condition or location of the goods. At the end of this section, we will review the success factors for IoT adoption in logistics and provide a roadmap on how logistics providers can move forward and leverage this trend.

Keywords: IoT, Autonomous System, Logistics, Arduino

1. INTRODUCTION

Amid the hype surrounding IoT today, one thing is clear: the logistics industry is a key player poised to benefit from the IoT revolution. With millions of shipments being moved, tracked, and stowed by a variety of machines, vehicles and people each day, it is no surprise that logistics and IoT are a perfect match. In logistics, IoT can connect different assets along a supply chain in a meaningful way, and then analyze the data generated from these connections to capture new insights. By doing so, IoT enables logistics providers to unlock higher levels of operational efficiency, while creating customized, dynamic, and automated services for their customers. Falling prices of device components (sensors, actuators and semiconductors), faster wireless networks, and increasing data crunching capabilities only compound the business benefits, ensuring that IoT becomes a disruptive trend in the logistics industry over the next decade.

1.1. Literature Review

Warehouses have always served as a vital hub in the flow of goods within a supply chain. But in today's economic climate, they also serve as a key source of competitive advantage for logistics providers who can deliver fast, cost-efficient, and increasingly flexible warehousing operations for their customers.

This is no easy challenge. With thousands of different types and forms of goods being stored in the average warehouse today, every square meter of warehousing space must be optimally utilized to ensure specific goods can be retrieved, processed, and delivered as fast as possible. The result is a high-speed, technology-driven environment that is ideal for IoT applications. From pallets and forklifts to the building infrastructure itself, modern warehouses contain many "dark assets" that can be connected and optimized through IoT. In the warehouse, the widespread adoption of pallet or item-level tagging — using low-cost, miniscule identification devices such as RFID — will pave the way for IoT-driven smart-inventory management. Let's examine a few instances of IoT in action in a warehouse. For starters, wireless readers capture data transmitted from each pallet as it arrives through inbound gateways. This data could include information on the product such as volume and dimensions, which could then be aggregated and sent to the WMS for processing. This capability eliminates the time-consuming task of manual counting and volume scanning of pallets. Cameras attached to the gateways could also be used for damage detection, by scanning pallets for imperfections.

Once pallets are moved to the right location, tags transmit signals to the WMS to provide real-time visibility into inventory levels, thus preventing costly of-stock situations. If any item has been misplaced, sensors can alert the warehouse manager, who can track the item's exact location for corrective action. quality management, sensors monitor the condition of item and alert warehouse managers when the temperature or humidity thresholds are about to be compromised. This would allow warehousing staff to corrective action, ensuring service quality and greater customer confidence. During outbound delivery, pallets are scanned through an outbound gateway to ensure that the right items – in the right order for delivery – are being sent. Stock levels are then updated automatically in the WMS for accurate inventory control.

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Beyond goods stored in a warehouse, IoT can also drive optimal asset utilization. By connecting machinery and vehicles to a central system, IoT enables warehouse managers to monitor all assets in real time. Managers can be alerted when an asset is being over-utilized or when an idle asset should be deployed to do other tasks. For example, a variety of sensors could be deployed to monitor how often assets in a sorting system, such as conveyer belts, are in use or idle, and at what times. Analysis of the data could then identify optimal capacity rates and tasks for the assets. Such solutions can in future identify inefficiencies in already automated processes.

2. METHODOLOGY

In this study we are dealing with the development of a Cloud platform for the Internet of Things (IOT) that can be used and will provide innovative solutions in different sectors (agriculture, demotic & home automation, smart cities etc) and in this case in logistics. The platform consists of two parts, the sensor network and the cloud server.

Sensor Network: consisting of autonomous nodes with sensors used to monitor physical or environmental conditions, such as temperature, humidity, atmospheric pressure, sound, etc. The network is capable of and give information to the cloud, and conversely to receive information to perform a specific energy (mainly on / off) via an actuator.

Cloud Server: is the database that receives all the information from the sensor network, the information is stored, processed and displayed in real time to a user from anywhere. Additionally, we are given the possibility to be able to control the remote sensor network.

The wireless sensor network consists of a central control node (gateway node) and one or multiple sensing node connected to each other via wireless antennas (apc220) in a star type topology.

The nodes (sensors) send periodic data every 15 minutes to the central node. The hub is connected to a router via Ethernet and data it collects, sends them to a database in the cloud. The nodes function implemented using microcontroller arduino* due to its low cost, ease of programming and the popular platform.

**It's a good choice for "experimental" level, for professional use can be replaced with other microcontrollers and sensors with the provided appropriate certification*

The main features of a wireless sensor network include:

- ✓ The energy consumption limits for nodes that use batteries
- ✓ Ability to deal node failures

- ✓ The mobility of nodes
- ✓ Communication failures
- ✓ The heterogeneity of nodes
- ✓ Escalation large scale growth
- ✓ Ability to withstand harsh environmental conditions
- ✓ Easy for Use

Each node is powered by rechargeable batteries (6600mAh) accompanied by a solar panel, making the autonomous system.

The system that is proposed is a complete autonomous control system based on microcontroller Arduino. For the implementation of the system microcontrollers and Arduino Mega Arduino Uno are being used, because of their low cost and low energy consumption (30-40 mA), characteristics that make them a good choice for use in the development of autonomous systems.

The Arduino Mega used as a central control node, where its role is to receive information from remote nodes with sensors that can be placed in various parts of the product. For the node with the sensors, the microcontroller Arduino uno is used, wherein the temperature sensors and air humidity were connected, and also the rain sensor.

For the power of the microcontroller, rechargeable batteries 5000 mah Cordless from a photovoltaic panel (2 watts), were used, and in order for the safety of microcontroller was used a specialist charge controller. After testing of the supply system, the duration of the microcontroller autonomy with associated sensors was about 100 hours.

For communication between the microcontroller radio antennas were used (APC220) with maximum 1Km communication distance that fully covered the needs of the implementation system.

The central control node receives information from remote nodes via the radio antenna. Through a GSM board when there is a change in the environmental conditions may give notice remotely via a sms message. Programming became via AT command by incorporating the programming language C ++ of arduino. Next was the addition of a static relay which serves as a switch, which can activate a specific computerized system. In programming bit microcontrollers, there were some difficulties mainly in finding libraries for individual components and sensors, but after reprogramming and appropriate configuration of the respective libraries difficulties were resolved.

Using this technology, dispatchers in the command center are able to assign directions and routes for the drivers, observe driver behavior, monitor the goods in real time, detect when a vehicle has gone off track, or even when a vehicle has been idle for too long. These containers are equipped with sensors that monitor the temperature and humidity levels. If either of the conditions rises higher or drops lower than the allowed range, an alert will be sent out to the dispatchers, who can then inform the truck driver to address the issue. These intelligent sensor technologies are perfect for large, international logistics companies that deliver goods over long distances, whether by land, air, or sea, so they are able to keep track of their cargo shipments. Intelligent sensors are also important for luxury goods, highly advanced consumer electronics, and pharmaceuticals, so dispatchers will know where the goods are, along with their estimated time of arrivals, and if they have been jeopardized in anyway.

3. RESULTS

The technology solution consists of an arduino node installed on each vehicle, the main components of each arduino node are the temperature sensor, a GPS antenna, a 3G antenna, using RFID or NFC technology, provide synchronized information and material flow in real time, operators are able to gather information on specified cargo at any time, instantaneously. With the help of these sensors, along with real-time locating systems, GPS tracking systems, and other information relaying tags, the objects are able to communicate with each other and disperse the information through the Internet in real time. Data is transferred into the cloud, and the devices can identify the pallet and not only share its position using GPS coordinates, but also bring in other data like weather conditions, traffic conditions, and driver-specific data (i.e., driving pattern, average speed). By tapping the data gathered by these technologies, detailed visibility of an item is provided all the way from the manufacturer to the retailer. Data gathered from GPS and RFID technologies not only allows supply chain professionals to automate shipping and delivery by exactly predicting the time of arrival; they can monitor important details like temperature control, which impact the quality of a product in-transit.

IoT can help supply chain professionals:

- Reduce asset loss. Know about product issues in time to find a solution.
- Save fuel costs. Optimize fleet routes by monitoring traffic conditions.
- Ensure temperature stability by monitoring the cold chain
- Manage warehouse stock. Monitor inventory to reduce out-of-stock situations.

Gain user insight. Embedded sensors provide visibility into customer behavior and product usage.

4. CONCLUSION

This autonomous control system based on microcontroller arduino that is suggested in this paper, and also with the support of a node with the necessary sensors, provides information in real time about the status of products and the security of containers during transport worldwide. The breadth of application highlighted in this report underscores how IoT is impacting virtually every sector of the logistics industry and society as a whole.

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